

Background

Plastics are widely used in the global economy, and each year at least 350 to 400 million tons are being produced. Due to poor recycling and low circular use, millions of tons are accumulated annually in terrestrial or marine environments. Since the 1990s research on the biodegradation of synthetic polymers has been promoted extensively owing to the universal concern about the global environmental crisis. Accordingly, the production of biodegradable polymerase has been gradually increasing but it still comprises a low percentage of total plastic production. Recently, an enzyme called PETase (Polyethylene Terephthalate digestive enzyme) has shown the ability to degrade the PET (Polyethylene Terephthalate) which is a polyester and non-degradable compound.

Plastic Usage Present scenerio

Plastic Pollution Is Growing

Total annual output of mismanaged plastic waste by coastal populations, top-ranked countries by billions of pounds

Percentage of marine species worldwide ingesting or entangled with plastic⁵

PETase enzyme

- Recently, a new discovered bacterium *Idonella sakaiensis* 201-F6, has shown the ability to grow on PET.
- The bacterium grows at a PH- 5.5 to 9 (optimum PH- 7 to 7.5) and a temperature of 15–42 °C (optimum temperature 30–37 °C).
- It secretes PET hydrolase or PETase enzyme.

Working Protocols

PETase degrades PET into MHET- Mono (2-hydroxyethyl) Terephthalic acid. The 2nd enzyme MHETase converts MHET into TPA- Terephthalic acid and EG- Ethylene glycol.

Fig: Methodology of PETase enzyme

Structure of PETase enzyme

Fig: (a) Graphical output of secondary structure of PETase enzyme. (b) Cartoon representation of PETase enzyme.

Active site

PET molecules will cleave at the substrate binding site of PETase enzyme. The catalytic triad is the conserved region comprising Ser160, Asp206 and His237. The expansion of the enzyme is achieved with minimal rearrangement of the adjacent loops and secondary structure.

Fig: (a) 3 residues- Ser160, Asp206 & His237 shown with cyan-coloured (b) Substrate binding site (c),(d) The side views of substrate binding site (e) H-bonds between residues & substrate shown with red coloured line. The 2-HE(MHET)4 is shown as an orange-coloured stick

Cost

Treatment with PETase enzyme is cost-effective as the enzyme is found in bacteria which is available in nature. Researchers found out that double mutant improved PET degradation capacity relative to wild type PETase. However, applying genetic engineering techniques on the enzyme will cost much less.

Conclusion

Obtaining plastic degradable enzymes and implementing them in the production of true biopolymers is a highly rewarding task and would significantly reduce our global plastic problem. Research on PET hydrolase is also contributing in new advances in biotechnological research. The process may take time but it will solve the plastic problem.

References

- Wei et al. 2019
- Joo et al. 2018
- Austin et al. 2018